

INTERFACIAL ADHESION BETWEEN CARBON FIBRE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES AND FOAM IN SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich structures comprising carbon fibre thermoplastic composite facesheets and polymeric foam cores provide high mechanical performance in combination with light weight. In order to ensure an effective stress transfer between the composite facesheet and the foam core, a strong interfacial adhesion between the two materials is a prerequisite. In this study, several investigations of the skin-core interface of sandwich structures are conducted, including physico-chemical interactions based on surface energies and mechanical interlocking influenced by foam surface morphology. The findings were compared against the experimentally measured adhesion forces via peel-off tests. The results suggest that both factors have a significant influence on the skin-core adhesion of the studied systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

Weight reduction has become a main driving force for many industry sectors, including automotive and aerospace applications. Lightweight composites including carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites and CFRTP-foam sandwich structures are highly suited for manufacturing a large number of automotive and interior aircraft components.

In this research, sandwich structures consisting of carbon fibre thermoplastic (Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene - ABS and Polysulfone - PSU) composite skins and foam cores (Polyethylene terephthalate - PET and Polyethersulfone – PES) are studied for use in interior aircraft applications. Sandwich parts with complex exterior shapes are formed to near netshape using the compression moulding technique, in which the composite skin is directly bonded to the foam core during sandwich processing. In order to understand the interfacial adhesion between the composite skin and the foam core, several investigations are conducted including physico-chemical interactions based on surface energies, experimental adhesion via peel-off test, and characterization of foam surface morphology. The developed fundamental understanding will provide practical guidelines regarding material selections for developing durable sandwich structures with limited skin-core debonding.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Carbon fibres in woven form were used as reinforcement for the composite face-sheets. Overall, four different material combinations for sandwich structures were tested. Two different thermoplastic matrices were used for this work, namely Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) and Polysulfone (PSU). Similarly, the two types of thermoplastic foams that were used for the sandwich core included Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and Polyethersulfone (PES) foams. These two foams also have significantly different surface morphology (Figure 1). The selected material systems are compatible in terms of processing window during compression moulding.

Figure 1. Surface morphology of foams characterized using optical 3D surface metrology technique

The surface morphologies of the two foams were characterised under an optical 3D surface metrology system, and the areas of solid surface (based on cell wall thickness) were estimated. The PET foam contains larger foam cells and thinner cell walls, which result in a smaller surface area (around 14% solid surface on the top surface of the foam) as compared to that of PES foam (around 37%).

2.2 Preparation of sandwich samples

The two carbon fibre reinforced skin materials were pre-consolidated in a hot press to achieve optimum impregnation and minimal thickness of remaining resin in between fibre plies. Large sandwich panels were then prepared by compression moulding process, in which the composite face-sheets were directly bonded to the foam core under applied high temperature and pressure, without using additional adhesive. Process parameters in terms of time, pressure and temperature for pre-impregnation and compression moulding were optimized in-house for best impregnation, consolidation and surface appearance (Figure 2). The sandwich panels were then cut to different sizes for the various tests.

Figure 2. Sandwich samples and a typical microscopic image of the cross section of CFRTP skin

2.3 Analysis of physico-chemical interaction at skin-core interface

The bonding between composite skin and foam core is mainly the adhesion of thermoplastic composite matrix and thermoplastic foam, most likely without significant chemical adhesion present [reference]. Therefore, physical adhesion is considered to play an important role for the interaction at the interface, which are effectively controlling the interface strength. Physical adhesion related to surface energies of the two neighbouring thermoplastic phases.

Surface energies of thermoplastic matrices and foam cores

Surface energies based on Owens–Wendt approach [1] of the matrix polymers and foams were determined using data of contact angles of the materials in various test liquids. In the Owens–Wendt approach, total surface energy, γ_S , is the sum of dispersive, γ_S^d , and polar, γ_S^p , components as shown in Eq. 1:

$$\gamma_S = \gamma_S^d + \gamma_S^p \quad (1)$$

Using the Wilhelmy technique, dynamic contact angles comprising advancing and receding angles can be determined. Based on these angles, the equilibrium contact angles, which were used for calculation of surface energy, were estimated [2, 3].

Work of adhesion and interfacial compatibility

The physical adhesion between foam and composite matrix can be measured by work of adhesion. The work of adhesion according to the Owens–Wendt approach can be calculated as follows:

$$W_a = 2 \left(\sqrt{\gamma_1^d \gamma_2^d} + \sqrt{\gamma_1^p \gamma_2^p} \right) \quad (2)$$

where the indices 1 and 2 refer to the thermoplastic matrix polymer and foam material, respectively. The interfacial energy is the reversible work of forming a unit of interface. It was proposed that minimizing the interfacial energy will yield a more stable system and hence increase the adhesive strength [2]. These expressions of the interfacial energy for two solid systems with surface energy components can then be described as in Eq.3

$$\gamma_{1-2} = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - 2 \left(\sqrt{\gamma_1^d \gamma_2^d} + \sqrt{\gamma_1^p \gamma_2^p} \right) \quad (3)$$

The work of adhesion and interfacial energy between different matrix-foam systems is an important parameter for predicting physical adhesion and compatibility at the interface.

2.4 Measurement of skin-core adhesion

The composite-foam adhesion was evaluated by peel-off tests which measure the peel torque needed to separate the flexible composite skin from the foam. The test was carried out using a climbing drum peel test set-up which follows ASTM D1781-98. The composite-foam adhesion was evaluated based on the average peel torque needed to separate the composite from the foam, which is calculated following Eq.4

$$T = (r_2 - r_1)(P - P_0)/w \quad (4)$$

where P is the average load required to bend and peel the skin adherend plus the load required to overcome the resisting torque; P_0 is load required to overcome the resisting torque; w is width of sample; r_1 and r_2 are radius of drum and radius of flange respectively.

The fracture surfaces of tested samples were also examined to understand failure mechanism of the sandwich samples and to study the foam surface morphology close to the interface.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical adhesion at skin-core interface

Surface energy of polymers

The surface energies of matrix polymers and foams were determined using the data of equilibrium contact angles of the materials in various test liquids [4, 5]. The measurements were carried out using the Wilhelmy technique on polymer film samples, measurement speed 1.5 mm/min, in three test liquids namely pure water, diiodomethane and ethylene glycol.

Figure 3. Surface energy components of polymers used for sandwich manufacture in this work

Surface energy comprising dispersive and polar components of the foams and the composite matrices was calculated following Owens–Wendt approach. The results are presented in Figure 3. It can be seen that the total surface energy of PES foam is higher than that of PET foam, while both foam materials have similar polar fraction. For the composite matrices, the surface energy of PSU is rather high and comparable to that of PES in terms of surface energy components. This can be explained by the fact that both PES and PSU belong to the same polysulfone family and have similar chemical compositions. Compared to PSU, the total surface energy of ABS is much lower.

Work of adhesion and interfacial energy

Figure 4. Work of adhesion and interfacial energy of foam-matrix systems

The works of adhesion and interfacial energy for the studied foam and polymers were calculated and are presented in Figure 4. Regarding the work of adhesion, the results show that the PSU matrix with both PET and PES foam system has a higher value compared to the ABS matrix system. This is due to the higher surface energy of PSU as shown previously in Figure 3. The highest work of adhesion can be found in PES/PSU system because of the high surface energies of the two polymers and low interfacial

energy. The work of adhesion directly reflects the significance of surface energies of the core and the skin materials, whereas a higher work of adhesion is expected to result in stronger physico-chemical interactions. In addition, the interfacial energy depending on the matching of surface energy components of foam and composite matrix also has an influence on the work of adhesion. Lower interfacial energy generally contributes to higher work of adhesion. For the studied polymers, PES and PSU are quite close in terms of chemical structure. Therefore, the mismatch in surface energy components between the two materials is small, which leads to low interfacial energy and high compatibility. In contrast, a combination of PES/ABS results in the highest interfacial energy which indicates a low compatibility between the two materials.

3.2 Practical adhesion of skin-core measured by peel torque

Figure 5. Typical peel force – displacement curve in climbing drum peel test

Figure 3 shows a typical peel force – displacement curve of the carbon fibre PSU composite and PET foam system (CF-PSU/PET). Here, the force increases while rolling the skin upwards via the climbing drum fixture, until debonding of the composite skin and foam core occurs. The interface crack then propagates while the peeling force is recorded. The force required for rolling of the skin alone is determined by testing a CFRTP skin sample without foam core, as also shown in Figure 5. This curves allows to determine an average value of P_0 for both composite systems.

Figure 6. Peel torque results of investigated sandwich systems

The average peel torque of CF-ABS and CF-PSU composites with two different foam cores (PET and PES) was calculated based on the peeling load, and the results are shown in Figure 6. Among the

four systems, it can be seen that the skin-core interfacial adhesion of the carbon composites bonded with PES foam requires a higher peeling torque than those with PET foam.

Figure 7. Fracture surfaces of sandwich peel test samples

Figure 7 presents the fracture surfaces of tested sandwich samples. For all four systems, it can be seen that the failure occurs along the composite-foam interface. Some fractured areas developed inside the foam cores, which indicates a strong interfacial adhesion between composites and foam cores, especially for sandwiches using PES foam. The lower peel torques in PET foam sandwich systems are attributed to the surface morphology of the PET foam which contains larger cells size and lower contact surface with composite skins.

3.3 Effects of material surface energies on the skin-core adhesion

In Figure 4, the peel torque of sandwich systems is also plotted together with the work of adhesion between foam and composite matrix in the sandwiches. It can be seen that the strength increase of the PET/PSU interface compared to PET/ABS correlates with the increased values for the work of adhesion. This shows the skin-core adhesion can be further improved by increasing the work of adhesion using high surface energy and compatible materials (foam and composite matrix). For cases with a lack of chemical bonds, physico-chemical adhesion plays an important role.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial adhesion between composite skins and foam cores in the studied sandwich structures is mainly controlled by physical adhesion based on cell morphology at the foam interface. We demonstrate good correlation between the results of the work of adhesion and those of experimental interface peel-off tests. We also highlight the effect of foam surface morphology on the composite-foam bond in sandwich structures with PET foam. The study provides an improved understanding on the interactions at skin-core interfaces which assist with the material section process in development of sandwich structures.

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REFERENCES

1. Owens, D.K. and R. Wendt, *Estimation of the surface free energy of polymers*. Journal of applied polymer science, 1969. **13**(8): p. 1741-1747.
2. Johnson, R. and R. Dettre, *Wetting of low-energy surfaces*. Vol. 49. 1993: Marcel Dekker, Inc.: New York.

3. Andrieu, C., C. Sykes, and F. Brochard, *Average spreading parameter on heterogeneous surfaces*. Langmuir, 1994. **10**(7): p. 2077-2080.
4. Connor, M., J.-E. Bidaux, and J.-A. Manson, *A criterion for optimum adhesion applied to fibre reinforced composites*. Journal of Materials Science, 1997. **32**(19): p. 5059-5067.
5. Tran, L.Q.N., et al., *Understanding the interfacial compatibility and adhesion of natural coir fibre thermoplastic composites*. Composites Science and Technology. **80**: p. 23-30.